

Study of Profile of Low Vision Patients, Their Clinical Evaluation, Trial of Low Vision Devices and Assessment of Visual Performance of Patients Examined in Low Vision Clinic in a Tertiary Eye Institute

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The purpose of study is to study the profile, methods of assessment and trial of various low vision devices of low vision patients in our tertiary eye institute.

Methods: A prospective, non- interventional observational study of 150 patients with low vision satisfying the WHO criteria for low vision was conducted over a period of 5 months in our tertiary eye institute after obtaining informed consent and considering the relevant inclusion and exclusion criteria. Patients were subjected to detailed history taking, a thorough ophthalmic examination and low vision assessment at low vision clinic. The suitable type, power and magnification of low vision devices was identified for each patient and trial given. The improvement in the optical performance with the low vision device was noted. The data thus obtained was recorded in excel sheet and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results: Out of 150 patients, males were 56.7% and 43.3% were females with mean age of 29.4 years. Most common cause of low vision was pathological myopia. 49.3% patients had difficulties in near tasks followed by combined near and distance tasks, difficulties in distance activities, issues with mobility and night vision. Dome magnifier was most common and accepted device prescribed [37.3%] for near tasks and binocular telescope for distance tasks [76.3%].

Conclusion: A thorough clinical evaluation of low vision patients is very important to identify their functional vision and needs. Tailored prescriptions based on individual clinical profiles and preferences are crucial for optimal outcomes.

Keywords: Low Vision, Optical Devices, Visual Performance, Clinical Profile.

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Introduction

Visual impairment which includes low vision and blindness is one of the leading public eye concerns to be addressed on priority basis. It can have lasting implications on Education, economic productivity, and social interactions. It can affect the quality of life in adults and children.

The World Health Organization [WHO] describes a person with low vision (LV) as one who has an impairment of visual function, even after treatment and/or standard refractive correction, and has a visual acuity (VA) of <6/18 to perception of light (PL), or a visual field of <10 degree from the point of fixation. [1]

Currently, there are about 285 million visually impaired globally and around 65 million in India. [2] Some of the common causes of low vision in adults include Uncorrected refractive errors, Cataracts, Glaucoma, Age related macular degeneration and Diabetic retinopathy. [3] In India, paediatric causes of visual impairment include Retinopathy of Prematurity, Vitamin A deficiency, Corneal disorders, Cataracts, Uncorrected refractive errors, Strabismus and Amblyopia. [4]

Early onset visual impairment in children can affect sensori-motor, language and cognitive development and scholastic performance.

Hence the need of the hour is to step up the low vision services for children and adults in our country for effective rehabilitation and improved quality of life.

Therefore, the study was undertaken to identify demographic characteristics, various modalities of visual assessment and trial of suitable low vision device for better visual performance of their activities of daily living.

Methods and Materials

A prospective, non-interventional, descriptive study of 150 patients aged above 9 years, referred to our low vision clinic at our tertiary eye institute was conducted over a period of 5 months. Prior Informed consent was obtained from all patients and the study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients satisfying the WHO criteria for low vision-Best corrected visual acuity [BCVA] in both eyes worse than 6/18 to FC at 1metre, visual fields <10° were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with co-existing neurological disorders, multiple disabilities and developmental delay were excluded [objective and subjective assessment would be difficult]. Patients with treatable causes of anterior segment and posterior segment pathology like media opacities and diabetic retinopathy were also excluded.

The patients with low vision were identified in the OPD/specialty clinics and thereby referred to low vision clinic for further assessment. All patients were evaluated by trained ophthalmologists.

Each patient was subjected to a detailed ocular assessment which included recording patient's demographic data, relevant ocular history, vision assessment with appropriate low vision charts, dry refraction was done with streak retinoscopy/autorefractometer and BCVA was recorded, wet refraction was done [wherever required], Anterior segment slit lamp examination, fixation test, visual field test by finger confrontation method, color vision and fundus examination.

Patient's daily requirements to perform various tasks were noted.

History taking included basic demographic data, duration of defective vision, history of previous eye trauma or surgery, usage of spectacles and low vision devices, family history of similar complaints and history of consanguinity was noted.

Vision assessment was done using ETDRS low vision Log MAR charts [alphabet/ tumbling E] at 3m or lesser monocularly and binocularly [unaided]

and with BCVA [Best corrected visual acuity] in place. [$\log \text{MAR}1 - \log \text{MAR}0$].

Near vision was assessed using Log MAR near charts at 25cm distance both monocularly and binocularly with BCVA in place [10M-0.8M].

Fixation testing was done monocularly to ascertain if it was central or eccentric.

The contrast sensitivity was evaluated using Hiding- Heidi low contrast test monocularly and binocularly [range- 25% to 1.25%].

Color vision was assessed with Ishihara chart and visual fields (finger confrontation) were assessed based on residual vision of the patient.

Using appropriate formula, the required magnification, power, and type of LVD was calculated. Patients were given a trial with low vision aids [optical and non-optical] based on the requirement, occupation and residual vision and improvement in visual performance noted.

Using following formula, the required magnification, power, and type of LVD was calculated.

$M=D+A/2.5$ where D is dioptic power and A is amplitude of accommodation.

A trial of low vision. The required power of magnification of low vision device was calculated and accepted device based on individual requirement was prescribed. The reading improvement with low vision device before and after was recorded using LogMAR chart for distance and near.

The various devices optical used for the trial included hand magnifier, dome magnifier, stand magnifier, spectacle magnifier, spectacle mounted binocular and monocular telescope, portable video magnifier. Non-optical aids included were NOIR filters, table lamp, typo-scope, reading stand and signature guide. After the low vision aids trial, patients were able to read small text and were able to see distant objects with suitable aids. All the data thus collected were recorded in Microsoft excel sheet and analysed using descriptive statistics.

Sample Size Calculation

$$n = \frac{Z_{\alpha/2}^2 pq}{d^2}$$

where $Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$

$p = 53.4$

$q = 100 - p = 46.6$

$d(\text{precision}) = 15\% \text{ of } p$

$d = 8.01$

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 53.4 \times 46.6}{(8.01)^2}$$

n=149

Results

A total of 150 patients were evaluated in low vision clinic of our tertiary eye institute. The mean age

was 29.4 years with minimum age of 9 years and maximum of 76 years. 55.3% of patients were between 16-40 years of age followed by children under 15 years of age (21.3%)- Table 1.

Table 1: Age distribution of low vision in our study

Age (In Years)	Frequency	Percentage
0-15	32	21.3
16-40	83	55.3
41-60	23	15.4
>60	12	8

The percentage of males were higher than females 85(56.7%) and 65(43.3%) respectively. 75(50%) patients had education only till 10th grade.

49.3% of patients had difficulty in near task, 32% of patients had complaints both difficulty in

reading and distant vision, 16% patients had difficulty in distant vision alone, 0.7% had difficulty in mobility in daylight and 1.3% patients had difficulty in night vision- Table 2.

Table 2: Main requirements of low vision patients

Main Need	Frequency	Percentage
Difficulty in Distant vision	24	16
Difficulty in night vision	2	1.3
Difficulty in near tasks	74	49.3
Difficulty in reading and Distant vision	48	32
Mobility in day light	1	0.7
Walking	1	0.7

66.7% of the patients had impaired colour vision. Fixation was central in 85.3% of patients and eccentric in 14.7% of patients. In majority causes of low vision were pathological myopia (17.3%), retinitis pigmentosa (16%), optic atrophy (10%), macular dystrophy (9.2%) followed by rod cone

dystrophy (8.7%), amblyopia (5.3%), albinism (4.7%), proliferative diabetic retinopathy (3.9%), nystagmus (3.9%), choroidal neovascular membrane (2.6%), retino choroidal coloboma (2%), stargardt's disease (2.7%)- Table 3.

Table 3: Diagnosis in low vision patients

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Age related macular degeneration [ARMD]	3	2
Advanced Glaucoma	2	1.3
Albinism	7	4.7
Amblyopia	8	5.3
Choroidal neovascular membrane [CNVM]	4	2.6
Coloboma	3	2
Congenital Cataract	2	1.3
Congenital infantile esotropia	1	0.7
Exudative Choroidal detachment	1	0.7
Hypertensive Retinopathy	1	0.7
High Hypermetropia	1	0.7
Keratoconus	1	0.7
Leber's Congenital Amaurosis	1	0.7
Macular dystrophy	14	9.2
Macular scar	1	0.7
Nystagmus	6	4
Optic atrophy	15	10
Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy	6	3.9
Pathological myopia	26	17.3
Retinitis Pigmentosa	24	16
Retino- choroidal coloboma	4	2.7

Retinopathy	1	0.7
Rod cone dystrophy	13	8.7
Stargardt's disease	4	2.7
Traumatic Optic Neuropathy	1	0.7

Near vision improvement: Before trial, 21.3% had unaided right eye near vision of 8M and 18.7% had unaided left eye vision of 8M. After trial of low vision aids, the near visual acuity improved to 1.6M in both eyes. The mean near vision before trial in both eyes was 6M with a standard deviation of 2.8. With device, the mean near vision improved

to 2.8M with a standard deviation of 1.7 in both the eyes 37.3% of patients were comfortable using dome magnifier followed by stand magnifier (19.3%), hand held magnifier (14.6%). 21 patients did not have improvement with near device- Table 4.

Table 4: Low vision devices prescribed for near vision

Aid for near vision	frequency	percentage
Dome magnifier	56	37.3
Stand magnifier	29	19.3
Hand held magnifier	22	14.6
Bar magnifier	14	9.3
Pocket magnifier	3	2
No improvement	17	11.3
Total	141	93.8%

The Non optical low vision aids were prescribed in 80% of patients and included NOIR filters, typoscope, table lamp, signature guide and walking canes.

Distant vision improvement: Unaided visual acuity was LogMAR1 in 52 patients (34.7%). after trial

with telescope 19.3% and 20% were able to read LogMAR0.6 from their right and left eye respectively. 76.3% patients were prescribed binocular telescope and 4.7% patients were prescribed mono ocular telescope. 22 patients (14.7%) did not have improvement with the aid- Table 5.

Table 5: Low vision devices prescribed for distance vision

Aid for distant vision	frequency	percentage
Binocular telescope	113	76.3
Monocular telescope	7	4.7
Prismatic spectacle	6	4
No improvement	22	14.8
Total	148	99.8%

Discussion

The essence of a comprehensive low vision service is the provision of suitable low vision aids. [5] These devices are likely to be beneficial because the inability to read is the most common complaint of patients with low vision. [6] However, the improvement in visual performance with low vision aids is often not recognized as there have been relatively few studies conducted for the same. [7]

This study was conducted in 150 subjects and has data presented from a population of patients visiting low vision clinic and provides a detailed analysis of ophthalmic patients with low vision.

The purpose of this study was to quantify the improvement in reading performance associated with the use of low vision aids and such studies are useful for further improvement in implementing and rehabilitation of the low vision patients. [8]

Age Distribution

In our study, 51.8% of them in the age group ranging 16-44 years which was comparable to other studies done by Mohindin et al, [9] Paudel P et al [10] and Olusanya et al [11] in which the patients below 50 years were 74%, 68% and 58% respectively. But in developed countries the age distribution pattern was found to be opposite as majority of the subjects were aged 60 years and above. [12,13] This could be attributed to that older population has also have good access to low vision clinics in developed countries.

Gender Distribution: Out of the 150 patients, 56.7% patients were male and 43.3% were females. There is pattern of male preponderance in studies quoted previously like our studies.

Causes of Low Vision: In the current study, major causes of low vision were pathological myopia (17.3%), retinitis pigmentosa (16%), optic atrophy

(10%), rod cone dystrophy (8.7%) followed by amblyopia (5.3%), retino-choroidal coloboma (2.7%) and Stargardt's disease (2.7%). In majority of the studies, the leading causes of low vision were posterior segment disorders which was like our study. A few other studies showed ARMD to be the leading cause of low vision in developed countries. [14,15] It was also noticed that majority (>50%) of the cases were either hereditary/congenital (retinitis pigmentosa, rod-cone dystrophy, albinism, etc). These results were comparable with a study done in Sudan. [16]

Low Vision Aids:

Near vision improvement: Before trial, 21.3% had unaided right eye near vision of 8M and 18.7% had unaided left eye vision of 8M. After trial of low vision aids, the near visual acuity improved to 1.6M in both eyes. The mean near vision before trial in both eyes was 6M with a standard deviation of 2.8. With device, the mean near vision improved to 2.8M with a standard deviation of 1.7 in both the eyes.

In comparison, the study by Gupta et al [17] found that near visual acuity in the right eye improved from 10M to 2M and in the left eye from 12M to 3M after using low vision aids. This suggests that both studies observed improvements in near visual acuity with low vision aids. Our study not only measured the improvement in visual acuity but also identified a subset of patients (21 in total) who did not benefit from the aids, thereby providing a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of these devices.

Distant Vision Improvement: For distant vision, our study reported that 52 patients (34.7%) had an unaided visual acuity of LogMAR 1. After trials with telescopic devices, 19.3% of patients could read LogMAR 0.6 with the right eye, and 20% could do so with the left eye. Additionally, 76.3% of patients were prescribed binocular telescopes, while 4.7% were given monocular telescopes. However, 22 patients (14.7%) did not show any improvement with these aids. In contrast, the study by Lee et al [18] found that distant visual acuity improved from LogMAR 0.8 to LogMAR 0.3 in the right eye, and from LogMAR 0.9 to LogMAR 0.4 in the left eye after using telescopic devices. Compared to our findings, the Lee et al. study showed a more substantial improvement in both eyes, indicating that the effectiveness of telescopic devices might vary depending on the specific characteristics of the patient population.

Conclusion

There is a strong need to spread awareness among the public regarding the availability of low vision services and enhancing their functional vision utilizing the appropriate low vision devices. There

is a huge gap in the population between the number of people with visual impairment and those having access to low vision services. Prompt referrals of patients with visual impairment is very essential to reduce the burden in the society. Further studies can be done in larger sample size and exploring other psychological issues and hindrances in accessing low vision services among patients with visual impairment.

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